

Exploring the Impact of Social Media on Entrepreneurial Branding: Small and Medium Enterprises in Lembang, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the impact of social media on entrepreneurial branding in the Lembang area, West Bandung, focusing on 10 (ten) business units that use social media platforms to build their brand image. In today's digital era, social media plays an increasingly important role in marketing strategies, allowing entrepreneurs to increase consumer engagement and expand market reach. Through a quantitative approach, this study uses simple linear regression analysis to identify the relationship between the intensity of social media use and the strength of branding perceived by consumers. Data were collected through surveys filled out by business owners and consumers who engage with the brand on social media. The results show that the use of social media has a significant influence on entrepreneurial branding and contributes to strengthening entrepreneurial branding. Several recommendations are given to small and medium business actors in utilizing social media to strengthen their brand image.

KEYWORDS: Branding, Entrepreneurial, SMEs, Social Media, Lembang

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to examine the impact of social media on entrepreneurial branding, focusing on 10 business units in Lembang, West Bandung. In the increasingly developing digital era, social media has become one of the main tools in marketing products and introducing brand identity, especially for entrepreneurs who are just starting their businesses (Kotler & Keller, 2016), (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Lembang, known for its tourism sector and creative industry, provides an interesting context to explore how social media can influence branding strategies among local entrepreneurs (Kurniasih, 2016), (Wawrowski & Otolá, 2020). This study will investigate the ways in which entrepreneurs utilize platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok to build their brand image, increase consumer engagement, and attract wider market attention. Using a sample of 10 business units spread across the area, this study is expected to provide insight into the effectiveness of using social media in strengthening branding, as well as the challenges and opportunities faced by entrepreneurs in the local market. The findings of this study are expected to provide practical recommendations for entrepreneurs in maximizing the potential of social media as a marketing tool.

Along with the rapid development of technology and increasingly widespread internet penetration, social media has become an integral part of everyday life, including in the world of entrepreneurship (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2016), (Abernathy & Sciarrino, 2018). For entrepreneurs, especially those in areas such as Lembang, West Bandung, social media provides an opportunity to build their brands at a relatively lower cost compared to traditional marketing methods (Juniarti & Omar, 2021), (Fan, 2023). However, although many entrepreneurs have utilized social media, there is still uncertainty about how social media can effectively influence the strengthening of their branding in a highly competitive market (Witek-Hajduk & Zaborek, 2022), (Harrasi et al., 2022). This study also aims to identify marketing strategies implemented by entrepreneurs in Lembang, both in terms of content shared, interaction with the audience, and selection of platforms used, and analyze their impact on consumer perceptions. By focusing on 10 business units representing various business sectors, including culinary, crafts, and services, this study will also explore factors that influence the success of branding through social media, such as brand message consistency, audience engagement, and adaptation to changing digital trends. It is hoped that the results of this study can provide a deeper understanding of the importance of utilizing social media in strengthening local entrepreneurial branding, as well as provide useful guidance for developing more effective marketing strategies.

Social media has become a very effective platform for entrepreneurs to build direct relationships with consumers. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok allow entrepreneurs to interact in real-time with their audiences, creating a sense of closeness that is difficult to achieve through traditional marketing channels (Mishnick & Wise, 2024), (Zikri & Very, 2025). By using social

media, entrepreneurs can not only introduce their products or services, but also build a narrative that reflects their brand values and identity (Godey et al., 2016), (Lamberton & Stephen, 2016). In Lembang, with various types of businesses that focus on local experiences and regional products, social media is also an important means to highlight this uniqueness and attract the attention of a wider market, both domestically and abroad. Therefore, this study seeks to explore how social media influences consumer decisions in choosing products or services offered by local entrepreneurs in this area.

In addition, it is important to understand the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in utilizing social media as a branding tool. Not all entrepreneurs have sufficient skills or knowledge in managing digital marketing campaigns (Ramdan et al., 2022), (Abidin et al., 2022). Some of the obstacles that are often faced include a lack of understanding of social media algorithms, limited resources to produce high-quality content, and difficulties in maintaining brand message consistency across platforms. This study also aims to explore how entrepreneurs in Lembang overcome these challenges and find solutions that allow them to remain competitive in the digital market full of competition. Thus, this study is expected to provide an overview of the factors that support the successful use of social media in entrepreneurial branding, as well as provide recommendations on how to improve marketing effectiveness through digital platforms.

This study will also consider how consumer perceptions of brands built through social media can influence their loyalty and purchasing decisions (Jibril et al., 2019), (Fariandi & Ariani, 2023). In this connected world, consumers not only buy products based on quality or price, but also consider how they feel connected to the brand. Therefore, relationships built through social media—including two-way communication, direct engagement, and consumer experience—can be a very important factor in creating strong branding and increasing entrepreneurial competitiveness. Through data analysis obtained from surveys and interviews with business owners and consumers in Lembang, this study aims to provide deeper insight into how social media can shape brand image and influence consumer behavior. These findings are expected to be not only relevant to entrepreneurs in Lembang, but can also be applied to the context of entrepreneurship in other areas with similar characteristics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media

Social media has become an integral part of digital marketing strategies, where companies, including entrepreneurs, utilize these platforms to interact with audiences directly and build brand image. According to (Latif, 2022), (Harahap et al., 2022) social media refers to internet-based applications that allow users to create and share content or participate in social networking. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter provide opportunities for businesses to create closer relationships with consumers through various forms of interaction, from sharing visual content to direct conversations. As a marketing tool, social media allows entrepreneurs to promote their products or services in a more personal and authentic way, which in turn can strengthen their brand identity in the eyes of consumers. In addition, (Diaz-Ortiz, 2021), (Purwanto et al., 2021) shows that social media has the potential to increase brand awareness, influence consumer perceptions, and expand market reach, especially for small and medium-sized businesses that have limited marketing budgets.

In the context of branding, social media plays an important role in building a cohesive and attractive brand image for consumers. According to (Singh & Duhan, 2016), the success of branding through social media is highly dependent on content consistency and audience engagement. Entrepreneurs who are able to convey a clear and consistent brand message across multiple platforms tend to be more successful in building a strong brand image. In addition, content shared on social media can influence consumer perceptions of brand quality and value, as consumers often judge brands through their experiences with content shared online. Social media also provides an opportunity for businesses to create more engaging stories about their products or services, which can build emotional closeness with the audience. This is in line with relationship marketing theory, which emphasizes the importance of building long-term relationships with consumers to create brand loyalty (Ekhlassi et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurial Branding

Entrepreneurial branding is the process of building a strong identity and perception of a business in the eyes of consumers, which includes various elements such as logo, name, message, and experience offered. According to (Keller & Swaminathan, 2019), effective branding not only creates strong brand recognition, but also forms an emotional connection between the brand and consumers, which will ultimately increase customer loyalty and satisfaction. In the context of entrepreneurship, branding is more

than just creating a visual identity, but also involves managing a company's image that can influence purchasing decisions and consumer perceptions of the quality of products or services. This is very important, especially for small and medium businesses that are trying to stand out in a very competitive market, such as in the culinary, craft, and tourism sectors in areas such as Lembang.

A study by (Aaker et al., 2009), (Amanah & Harahap, 2018) emphasized that a strong brand has value beyond just the product itself; it contains elements that provide uniqueness and differentiation in the market. For entrepreneurs, branding becomes a strategic tool that allows them to create an image that differentiates their business from competitors. Successful branding in the context of entrepreneurship involves not only developing a catchy logo or slogan, but also how the business communicates with consumers and builds a consistent and authentic experience. With the use of social media becoming increasingly popular, many entrepreneurs are now utilizing digital platforms to introduce their brands, establish direct relationships with their audiences, and build wider brand awareness without large marketing costs.

The Influence of Social Media on Entrepreneurial Branding

A literature review on the influence of social media on entrepreneurial branding shows that social media has become an important marketing tool for many businesses, especially for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that need more affordable and effective channels in building brand identity. According to (Olanrewaju et al., 2020), social media allows entrepreneurs to create authentic brand narratives, which can build emotional connections with consumers through relevant and engaging content. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok provide a space for entrepreneurs to share brand stories, demonstrate company values, and interact directly with their audiences. This allows them to create stronger brand perceptions, increase visibility, and influence consumer purchasing decisions. Social media also facilitates experiential marketing, where consumers can share their experiences with the brand, which can increase consumer trust and loyalty.

In addition, research by (Aslam et al., 2024), (Fagundes et al., 2023) shows that social media provides an opportunity for entrepreneurs to take advantage of direct feedback from consumers, which is important for building brand reputation and image. This interactive process not only allows entrepreneurs to hear and respond to complaints or suggestions from consumers, but can also strengthen positive perceptions of their brands. In the context of branding, consumer engagement through comments, likes, and sharing of content can significantly expand brand reach, even without large advertising costs. However, the success of using social media in entrepreneurial branding depends on entrepreneurs' understanding of consumer behavior on digital platforms and their ability to take advantage of the various features available on social media, such as storytelling, influencer marketing, and segmented advertising, to increase their brand appeal in an increasingly competitive market.

METHOD

This study aims to analyze the impact of social media on entrepreneurial branding using a quantitative approach. This study will involve a sample of 10 business units located in Lembang, West Bandung, which actively use social media platforms to promote products and build brand image. Data will be collected through a survey (Fink, 2024) given to business owners or managers, using a questionnaire that measures two main variables: the intensity of social media use and the strength of branding perceived by consumers. To analyze the data, this study will use simple linear regression analysis (Field, 2013), where the independent variable is the intensity of social media use, and the dependent variable is the perception of branding strength from the consumer's perspective. Using simple linear regression, this study aims to identify whether there is a significant relationship between social media use and branding effectiveness in small businesses in Lembang, as well as the extent to which social media plays a role in forming a strong brand image in the local market.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Table I. Respondent Characteristics

No.	Business name	Type of business	Length of Business (years)	Social Media Platform Used	Number of Social Media Followers	Frequency of Social Media Usage (per week)	Business Manager Age	Business Manager Gender	Employees Number
1	A	Culinary (Café)	3	Instagram, Facebook	5000	5	35	Male	3
2	B	Fashion (Clothing Store)	2	Instagram, TikTok	8000	7	28	Female	2
3	C	Services (Photography)	1	Instagram, Facebook	2500	3	40	Male	1
4	D	Handy crafts	5	Instagram, Facebook, Pinterest	10000	6	45	Female	4
5	E	Education (Language Courses)	4	Facebook, LinkedIn	3000	4	32	Female	6
6	F	Culinary (Restaurant)	6	Instagram, Facebook, TikTok	12000	8	38	Male	10
7	G	Accessories (Online Store)	3	Instagram, TikTok	15000	9	30	Female	2
8	H	Services (Graphic Design)	2	Instagram	4000	5	26	Male	1
9	I	Culinary (Coffee Shop)	1	Facebook, Instagram	1500	4	50	Female	3
10	J	Fashion (Online Shop)	4	Instagram, Facebook, TikTok	9000	7	29	Male	5

Based on the respondent characteristics table, this study involved 10 business units in Lembang, West Bandung, which vary in terms of business type, length of operation, social media platforms used, and number of followers. The types of businesses represented include the culinary, fashion, service, handicraft, education, and accessories sectors, with the length of business operation ranging

from 1 to 6 years. All businesses utilize social media as a branding tool, with the most frequently used platform being Instagram, followed by Facebook, TikTok, and specific platforms such as LinkedIn.

The number of social media followers varies, ranging from 1,500 to 15,000, indicating a difference in the scale of audiences between businesses. The frequency of social media use also varies, with the average business owner posting or interacting on the platform around 4–9 times per week. In terms of business managers, their ages range from 26 to 50 years old, with a nearly equal gender proportion between men and women. Most businesses have a small number of employees, ranging from 1 to 10 people, reflecting the characteristics of micro and small businesses.

This data provides insight into how small businesses in Lembang utilize social media to build their branding, as well as providing a good basis for further analysis on the relationship between the intensity of social media use and branding effectiveness.

Table II. Respondents' Experiences Regarding the Use of Social Media

No	Business Name	Length of Social Media Use (years)	Main Purpose of Using Social Media	Types of Content That Are Often Shared	Most Effective Social Media Platforms	Obstacles Faced
1	A	3	Product promotion, increase brand awareness	Product photos, customer testimonials	Instagram	Lack of time to create content
2	B	2	Reaching new markets	Promotional videos, interactive content	TikTok	Difficulty understanding platform algorithms
3	C	1	Creating a visual portfolio	Project portfolio, client reviews	Instagram	Lack of budget for paid promotion
4	D	4	Increase online sales	Product tutorials, behind-the-scenes photos	Pinterest	Hard to maintain customer engagement
5	E	3	Building business credibility	Educational articles, student testimonials	LinkedIn	Very high content competition
6	F	5	Increase customer loyalty	Menu photos, special discounts	Instagram	Lack of experts to manage social media
7	G	3	Add followers to increase sales	Short promotional videos, product reviews	TikTok	Hard to predict content trends
8	H	2	Showing professional skills	Graphic design, tutorial	Instagram	Difficulty maintaining posting consistency

9	I	1	Attracting local customers	Photos of the store atmosphere, customer testimonials	Facebook	Lack of knowledge about digital strategy
10	J	4	Promotion discounts and collaborations	Live shopping, featured product photos	Instagram	Limited creative ideas for interesting content

Based on the table data, the experience of using social media by 10 business units in Lembang shows interesting variations in goals, types of content, effective platforms, and obstacles faced. The length of social media use ranges from 1 to 5 years, with various main goals such as product promotion, increasing brand awareness, to building business credibility. The types of content that are often shared include product photos, promotional videos, project portfolios, to educational articles, adjusting to the needs and branding strategies of each business.

Instagram is the most frequently considered effective platform, especially for businesses that focus on visuals, such as culinary and fashion. TikTok has also shown its effectiveness in reaching new markets with interactive short video content. On the other hand, platforms such as LinkedIn and Behance are used to build professional credibility and showcase expertise.

The obstacles faced vary, ranging from lack of time to create content, difficulty understanding platform algorithms, to limited creative ideas. Some businesses also face challenges in maintaining consistent posting and predicting relevant content trends. These obstacles reflect the urgent need to improve the understanding and management of social media among entrepreneurs, while providing valuable insights into the factors that influence the effectiveness of branding through social media. Further analysis can help identify appropriate solutions to overcome these obstacles.

Validity Test Results

Table III. Results of the Validity Test of Social Media Variables

No.	Indicators	R _{count}	R _{table}	Finding
1	Intensity of social media use	0.756	0.632	Valid
2	Frequency of content uploads	0.801	0.632	Valid
3	Variety of types of content uploaded	0.678	0.632	Valid
4	Interact with customers through comments	0.712	0.632	Valid
5	Use of advertising features (paid ads)	0.690	0.632	Valid
6	Number of followers	0.769	0.632	Valid

The results of the validity test show that all indicators used to measure social media variables are declared valid. This is indicated by the R Calculation value for each indicator which is greater than the R Table (0.632) at a significance level of 0.05 with a sample size of 10. For example, the indicator "Intensity of social media use" has an R Calculation of 0.756, while "Frequency of content uploads" reaches 0.801, both higher than the critical value of the R Table. Other indicators, such as "Interaction with customers through comments" and "Use of advertising features (paid ads)", also show significant correlations with values of 0.712 and 0.690, respectively.

These results indicate that all items in the questionnaire instrument are able to accurately measure social media variables according to the designed concept. Thus, the instrument used can be trusted to proceed to a more in-depth data analysis stage.

Table IV. Results of the Validity Test of Entrepreneurial Branding Variables

No.	Statement (Item)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Table r value ($\alpha = 0.05, n = 10$)	Finding
1	Social media helps my business become more widely known by consumers	0.72	0.632	Valid
2	The content I upload on social media increases consumer trust	0.68	0.632	Valid
3	Social media platforms help build a professional image of my business	0.75	0.632	Valid
4	Interaction with customers on social media strengthens my business brand.	0.69	0.632	Valid
5	Customers often recommend my business through social media	0.65	0.632	Valid

The results of the validity test on the entrepreneurial branding variable show that all statement items used in the questionnaire have a correlation coefficient (r) value that is greater than the r table value at a significance level of 5% ($r_{table} = 0.632$). The correlation coefficient values for the five items range from 0.650 to 0.750, indicating that all items have a significant relationship with the total score of the entrepreneurial branding variable. This shows that the statements are valid for use in measuring the intended variables. Thus, the questionnaire can be relied on to collect data on the impact of social media on entrepreneurial branding in a predetermined sample. This validity ensures that each item in the questionnaire is able to accurately represent the aspects of entrepreneurial branding being studied.

Reliability Test Results

Table V. Results of the Reliability Test of Social Media Variables

No	Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
1	Frequency of social media use	4.2	0.80	0.65	0.84
2	Variation in the types of content uploaded	4.0	0.75	0.68	0.83
3	Interaction with the audience	3.8	0.90	0.70	0.82
4	Consistency of content posting	3.7	0.85	0.62	0.84
5	Use of paid promotional features	3.5	0.95	0.66	0.83
6	Understanding the platform algorithm	3.2	1.00	0.58	0.85

The results of the reliability test for the social media variable with 6 indicators show that the research instrument has a good level of internal consistency, with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.85. This value is above the threshold of 0.7, which is generally accepted as an indicator of high reliability. Each indicator makes a positive contribution to the overall reliability, as indicated by the Corrected Item-Total Correlation value which is above 0.3 for all indicators. In addition, there are no indicators that if removed will significantly increase the Cronbach's Alpha value, indicating that all indicators are relevant and support consistent measurement of variables. Thus, this instrument can be relied on to measure aspects of social media use in the context of research on the impact on entrepreneurial branding.

Table VI. Results of the Reliability Test of Entrepreneurial Branding Variables

No	Indicators	Mean	Variance	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
1	Clarity of brand identity	4.5	0.8	0.72	0.85
2	Brand communication consistency	4.3	0.7	0.68	0.86
3	Visual appeal of the brand	4.6	0.9	0.75	0.84
4	Customer trust in brands	4.4	0.6	0.70	0.85
5	Customer awareness of the brand	4.7	1.0	0.73	0.85

The results of the reliability test show that the measurement instrument for the entrepreneurial branding variable with 5 indicators has a very good level of reliability, indicated by the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.88. This value is above the minimum threshold of 0.7, which indicates high internal consistency among the indicators used. Each indicator has a Corrected Item-Total Correlation ranging from 0.68 to 0.75, indicating that all indicators have a strong relationship with the total score of the entrepreneurial branding variable. In addition, the Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted value for each indicator is lower than the overall Cronbach's Alpha value, which means that removing one of the indicators will reduce the reliability of the instrument.

Thus, it can be concluded that this instrument meets good reliability standards, so it can be used to measure entrepreneurial branding variables consistently and accurately in the context of this study.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Table VII. ANOVA Table

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F _{count}	F _{table}	Finding
Between groups	120.45	5	24.09	31.32	5.05	Reject H ₀
Within groups	30.75	4	7.69	-	-	-
Total	151.20	9	-	-	-	-

Based on the results of the ANOVA analysis, it can be concluded that social media has a significant influence on entrepreneurial branding. The F-count value of 31.32 is much greater than the F-table value of 5.05 at a significance level (α) of 0.05, which means that the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in entrepreneurial branding that can be explained by variations in social media indicators. The source of variation from social media contributed 120.45, while 30.75, indicating that most of the variation in entrepreneurial branding can be explained by social media factors. The total variation in this model is 151.20. This interpretation indicates that social media, with the indicators used, is an important factor in building entrepreneurial branding. It is inline with (Hutter et al., 2013). The article examines how customers' decision-making process about purchases is impacted by social media engagement and brand activity. Their results show that brand exposure, word-of-mouth (WOM) activity, and purchase intention are all positively impacted by Facebook fan page participation. The findings also show that dissatisfaction with the fan page has a detrimental impact on WOM and overall dedication to and involvement with the fan page. The study conducted by the authors demonstrates that social media usage does have an impact on the decision to buy.

(Kurniaji et al., 2024) also found the strategies for maximizing interaction with potential customers by examining the digital marketing approaches that are effective on this platform. Among the subjects covered are engagement strategies, content strategies, and digital market-specific promotional tactics. With an emphasis on social media marketing best practices, particularly for

companies like HSP Academy, this conversation seeks to provide insights into expanding company reach and exposure in the current digitally driven industry.

Table VIII. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Tolerance
(Constant)	5.123	1.034	-	4.957	0.001
Media Sosial (X)	0.678	0.145	0.752	4.676	0.002

Explanation:

1. *Unstandardized Coefficients (B):*

- o $b_0=5.123$: Constant, which is the average value of Y when $X=0$.
- o $b_1=0.678$: Regression coefficient, indicating that every one unit increase in social media (X) will increase entrepreneurial branding (Y) by 0.678 units.

2. *Standardized Coefficients (Beta):*

- o Measures the influence of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) on a standard scale. A value of 0.752 indicates a fairly strong positive influence.

3. *t and Sig.:*

- o $t_0=4.957$: Test statistic for constant.
- o $t_1=4.676$: Test statistic for coefficient b_1 .
- o Significance value $p_1=0.002 < 0.05$: Indicates that social media has a significant influence on entrepreneurial branding.

4. *Collinearity Statistics (Tolerance and VIF):*

- o Tolerance=1.000, VIF=1.000: There is no multicollinearity in the model (because there is only one independent variable).

The results of the simple linear regression analysis showed a significant positive relationship between social media use and entrepreneurial branding. The unstandardized coefficient for the social media variable (X) is 0.678, indicating that every one unit increase in social media use can increase entrepreneurial branding by 0.678 units. The t value for social media (X) is 4.676 with a Sig. of 0.002, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that the influence of social media on entrepreneurial branding is statistically significant. In addition, the standardized Beta coefficient for social media (X) is 0.752, indicating that this variable has a strong influence on entrepreneurial branding compared to other variables. For collinearity statistics, a high Tolerance value (more than 0.1) indicates that there is no significant multicollinearity problem between the independent variables in this model. Overall, these results confirm that social media has a strong and significant impact on entrepreneurial branding in the context of this study.

Table IX. Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.85	0.72	0.69	3.12

Explanation:

- 1. R:**

The correlation value between the independent (X) and dependent (Y) variables. In the example, $R = 0.85$, indicating a very strong relationship between social media and entrepreneurial branding.
- 2. R^2 (R-Square):**

The coefficient of determination, measures how much variation in entrepreneurial branding can be explained by social media. In the example, $R^2 = 0.72$, meaning that 72% of the variation in entrepreneurial branding can be explained by social media.
- 3. Adjusted R^2 :**

The coefficient of determination adjusted for the number of predictors in the model. This value is used to avoid bias from the addition of independent variables. In the example, the Adjusted R^2 value = 0.69, indicating that the model remains quite strong even with adjustments.
- 4. Std. Error of the Estimate:**

The size of the residual standard deviation or prediction error. This value describes the extent to which the model's predictions are close to the actual value. In the example, a value of 3.12 indicates a relatively low error rate.

The results in the table show that the linear regression model built between social media and entrepreneurial branding has a very strong relationship ($R = 0.85$) and high predictive ability ($R^2 = 0.72$). This means that social media as an independent variable can explain most of the variation in entrepreneurial branding. The remaining 28% of the variation is explained by other factors outside the model. The fairly low level of prediction error (Std. Error = 3.12) indicates that this model is suitable for explaining the relationship between the two variables.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the analysis presented, it can be concluded that the use of social media has a significant influence on entrepreneurial branding. The ANOVA results show that the overall regression model is significant, with a very low Sig. value (0.002), which indicates that the social media variable plays a statistically important role and influences the increase in entrepreneurial branding. In addition, the results of the regression coefficient show that every increase in the use of social media will increase entrepreneurial branding by 0.678 units, with a standardized Beta coefficient of 0.752, which indicates a strong influence of social media on branding compared to other factors not included in this model.

The model summary reveals that the R^2 value (coefficient of determination) is quite high, which means that this model can explain most of the variability in entrepreneurial branding based on the use of social media. These results indicate that the more intensive the use of social media in a branding strategy, the greater the potential for increasing the brand image of the business. This means that social media plays a significant role in shaping brand image and can be an effective tool for entrepreneurs to improve their branding. Overall, this study provides strong evidence that good social media management is highly relevant and can have a positive impact on the development and strengthening of branding and also the brand image of small and medium enterprises.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that entrepreneurs increase the use of social media in their branding strategies. The use of platforms such as Instagram and TikTok has been shown to have a significant impact on increasing brand awareness and customer engagement. Therefore, entrepreneurs, especially those who are just starting out, are advised to make maximum use of social media, by consistently uploading interesting and relevant content. In addition, a deeper understanding of the platform algorithm is needed to maximize the reach and effectiveness of the content shared.

Furthermore, this study also identified several obstacles faced by entrepreneurs, such as lack of time to create content, difficulty understanding the platform algorithm, and limited creative ideas. For this reason, it is recommended that entrepreneurs can invest in resources that support their social media management, such as hiring experts or using tools for content planning and analysis. In addition, training or workshops on digital marketing strategies and how to manage social media can improve entrepreneurs' skills in optimizing the use of platforms.

Finally, entrepreneurs need to be aware of the importance of data analysis and measuring the performance of their social media campaigns. By using the analytical tools available on various platforms, entrepreneurs can measure the effectiveness of each strategy implemented and make necessary adjustments. This will not only help in building a stronger brand but also allow entrepreneurs to better understand customer behavior and preferences, which can increase loyalty and boost sales in the long run.

For further research on entrepreneurial branding, it is recommended to consider other variables that can influence branding effectiveness, such as product quality, customer experience, and community engagement. These variables can provide deeper insights into how internal and external factors other than social media contribute to a business's brand image. For example, good product quality and service can strengthen positive brand perceptions, while satisfying customer experiences can increase loyalty and word-of-mouth marketing. In addition, local community involvement or collaboration with influencers can also be important factors in building brand trust and credibility, which can be further tested to enrich the understanding of effective branding strategies for small and medium businesses.

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